

The Application of Augmented Reality in Accounting Education: A Systematic Literature Review

Renren Cao, Kien Tsong Chau*, Wan Ahmad Jaafar Wan Yahaya, Chen Yan, Tan Li

Currently, the integration of augmented reality technology and accounting education has aroused significant concentration. The objectives of this study are to analyze and synthesize contemporary research on the integration of augmented reality technology into accounting education. This paper analyses four studies and scrutinizes the augmented reality technology applications in accounting education, including the current state, types of equipment utilized and the benefits, shortcomings, and future tendencies. Research shows that the application of augmented reality technology in accounting education has great potential and good prospects. However, it still exists some limitations, including high equipment costs and a lack of technological maturity.

Key words: *Augmented Reality, Accounting Education, Educational Technology, Systematic Review*

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INTRODUCTION

Augmented reality technology has triggered significant advancements in the education field thanks to its extraordinary interactivity and immersive capabilities. Over the past few years, the integration of augmented reality technology and accounting education has garnered extensive attention. Meanwhile, numerous studies on accounting education have begun to utilize augmented reality as an education technology tool to strengthen understanding accounting abstract concepts and terms. The combination of contemporary teaching technology can significantly enhance conventional accounting instruction, providing an effectual learning practice for students. However, this requires teachers to possess a certain level of technical proficiency and to adapt their teaching approach to incorporate the curriculum model with modern technology (Zhang, S., & Yao, Z., 2025). As a new teaching instrument, it has changed the pattern of accounting education. The research objective is to analyze and synthesize current studies on the utilize of augmented reality technology in accounting exploration. The primary focus is to summarize the current status, types, advantages, and disadvantages in the research over the past five years. The study is distributed into six parts. The first part introduces the research content. The second part summarizes the background of the research and the literature review in accounting. The third part states the methods of this study. The fourth part states the main results of this study. Finally, the fifth part presents the conclusions of this study. The last part discusses the limitations and future works of this study.

Systematic Review on Augmented reality technology

Augmented Reality is a technology that creates mixed or 'physical-digital' experiences (Heller et al., 2019; Kowalczyk, et al., 2021). It combines real-world and virtual images, facilitating synchronized interaction between them (Azuma, 1997; Maas & Hughes, 2020). Rather than completely replacing reality, Augmented Reality enriches it (Azuma, 1997; Carmigniani et al., 2011; Wither et al., 2011). It enhances students' interaction by overlaying AR components (images and animations) onto a real-world background (Billinghurst, Kato, & Poupyrev, 2001). When barcodes or markers are scanned, virtual elements merge with real-world data. This allows individuals to observe virtual images while staying connected to the real world (Yilmaz & Goktas, 2017).

Augmented Reality utilizes image recognition technology in smartphone to detect locations, pictures, markers, or objects that can be overlaid onto the real world. Azuma (1997) states that Augmented Reality systems possess three key features, namely virtual objects and real world integration, real-time interaction, and 3D virtual objects incorporation. Milgram and Kishino (1994) present the reality-virtuality continuum to clarify the distinctions between Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality, and Mixed Reality.

Students utilizing VR technology have the feasibility of encountering an immersive virtual setting. Contrarily, the students demonstrated an innovative way of interaction by using AR technology to enhance the real environment with digital elements. Unlike VR, the function of AR is mainly the integration of digital (virtual) domain and physical (real) environment (Garrett et al., 2018).

Learning with AR can achieve a ubiquitous learning experience (Cárdenas-Robledo & Peña-Ayala, 2018), collaborative (Marques et al., 2021) and localized learning (Martins et al., 2022). It enables virtual objects to appear in real-world space in real time. AR is an emerging technology with high potential for learning, teaching, and creative training (Avila-Garzon et al, 2021). An Augmented Reality system provides rich contextual data such as location information, audio, and video. It also provides 3D information to enhance the interactive experience.

Numerous studies have utilized augmented reality technology in accounting education. A recent study shows that a prototype app combining augmented reality and AI-based language translation effectively teaches accounting in IsiZulu. Students found ZART easy to use, engaging due to its avatars, and helpful for learning basic accounting concepts (Ade-Ibijola, A. et al., 2025). Liew et al. (2018) investigated the impact of augmented reality-enhanced textbooks on accounting knowledge. By capturing augmented reality, this technology enables researchers to obtain a deeper understanding of how viewers perceive the accounting education. Therefore, the article describes the development process of augmented reality and accounting.

Methodology

The study states a systematic literature review, and the researchers adopted systematic review and meta-analysis. Additionally, the research questions of the study are as follow:

- (1) What is the current state of development of research on the use of augmented reality technology in accounting education?
- (2) What types of Augmented Reality technologies are used in accounting education?
- (3) What are the advantages of using Augmented Reality in accounting education?
- (4) What are the challenges of using Augmented Reality in accounting education?

Search strategy

As a research sample, accounting is generally considered an applied discipline within business education in higher education. It is interdisciplinary in nature, drawing on knowledge from mathematics, information technology, and cultural or social contexts. Therefore, the study used 3 databases for searching: ProQuest, Web of Science, Scopus. These papers were published between 2020 and 2025. Search terminology included blends of keywords such as “augmented reality” and “accounting.” These terms were used to search the titles, abstracts, and keywords of articles, and references of included articles were manually screened to identify relevant studies that met the inclusion criteria but were not found in the database searches. As far as we know, the Web of Science contains high-impact journals, conference papers, and books from around the world. ProQuest provides comprehensive access to international theses and dissertations through its PQDT database. Scopus covers journal articles, conference papers, book chapters, and other documents in multiple fields as well as offers powerful bibliometric analysis tools.

Eligibility review

To obtain papers relevant to this study from the 179 kinds of literature, the researchers used sample, the phenomenon of interest, design, evaluation, and research type model (SPIDER) as a framework to formulate eligibility criteria in the study. SPIDER is a standardized, systematic search strategy that facilitates rigor in research (Cooke et al., 2012). This study used both tools to identify systematic reviews and meta-analyses by applying exclusion and inclusion criteria. As shown in Table 1.

Table1. Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Paper published between 2020 and 2025.	Papers older than 2020.
The full paper is written in English.	Non-English
Applying augmented reality to the field of learning accounting	Augmented Reality devices are used in other fields, except accounting.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the study

Methods

The goal of this study is to review relevant research that has been published within a specific period. We adopt a systematic literature review approach to analyze the unique issues faced by augmented reality in accounting education from both narrative and taxonomic perspectives. In doing so, we observed the manual set out in the PRISMA report (Page et al., 2021). After screening according to the pre-set criteria, we identified a total of 179 articles, of which 6 were duplicates, 141 were unrelated to augmented reality in accounting education, 3 were non-English studies, and 58 were published before 2020. Finally, four papers met the requirements. The detailed information on these articles is shown in Table 2:

Table 2. The four articles of the study

No	Title	Author	AR types	Advantages
1	Teaching accounting principles using augmented reality and artificial intelligence-generated IsiZulu language translations	Ade-Ibijola, A., et al	QR code	Zulu augmented reality translation has important implications for academics and accounting students.
2	Developing augmented reality-based learning media and users' intention to use it for teaching accounting ethics	Hadi, S. H. et al	AR-mark er	Augmented reality mobile application that teaches accounting ethics to college students using revenue recognition cases. It helps students understand accounting ethics.
3	Examining Future Ready Accounting Course (FRAC) Experiences for Non-accounting Students: An Education in Society 5.0 Using Augmented Reality and IoT	Zainudin, S. A., et al	None	Embedding augmented reality technology in teaching activities can improve student performance.
4	Accountants Of The 21st Century: Developing professional Competencies For Industry 4.0	Guagha, et al	None	Augmented Reality influence accounting by enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and data security. These can enhance accountants' efficiency.

Results

The study objective is to systematically scrutinize the present states, types, advantages and disadvantages of Augmented Reality technology applications in accounting education. By synthesizing current study results, we aim to identify the application of Augmented Reality technology in accounting education as well as assess its effect on teaching achievements. In addition, we will also explore important issues encountered in practical applications to provide reference for future educational practice. The paper will discuss the following four parts:

What is the current state of development of research on the use of augmented reality technology in learning accounting?

Between 2020 and 2025, four related studies were conducted. This suggests that, although research in this field is relatively new, the integration of augmented reality technology and accounting education has aroused increasing attention over time. Overall, research in accounting education is still in its development stage and has not yet produced a stable study result. There are currently four studies in accounting education that utilize augmented reality as the primary tool, providing preliminary theoretical and empirical support for this field. However, more systematic research is still necessary to further develop this field.

What types of AR technologies are used in accounting education?

The classification of augmented reality technology requires comprehensive consideration of multiple factors relevant to the technology and its potential capabilities, including hardware devices, tracking systems, and display technologies. There are diverse types of technologies in which Augmented Reality can be employed, each pursuing diverse objectives or applications, as mentioned below: marker-based Augmented Reality, Augmented Reality not based on markers, Augmented Reality based on projections, and AR based on overlaps (Arena et al., 2022). In this article, accounting education focuses solely on the AR-marker types. As shown in table 2.

What are the advantages of using Augmented Reality in accounting education?

Augmented reality technology is converting the way accounting education is taught, merging virtual elements with real-world environments to provide educators with dynamic and engaging teaching tools. Traditional accounting instruction is often limited to static materials and limited hands-on resources, limiting the breadth and depth of student learning. AR technology can help overcome these challenges by creating an interactive, immersive learning experience that increases student engagement and deepens understanding. Augmented Reality technology not only inspires students' motivation to learn and improves their participation but also aids them in comprehending complicated conceptions more intuitively, cultivating their spirit of inquiry and practical ability (Han & Luo, 2024), as shown in Table 2.

What are the challenges of using Augmented Reality in accounting education?

Some limitations and shortcomings have been demonstrated that cannot be ignored. Numerous universities may be not capable to implement top-quality augmented reality instruments and content thanks to insufficient cost and technological support. Additionally, some teachers may lack the necessary understanding and confidence in this new technology to integrate it into their teaching effectively (Wang et al., 2017). The implementation of AR involves processing large amounts of data, which raises issues related to the protection of personal information. As the application of AR technology in education becomes increasingly widespread, protecting the data privacy of students and teachers, as well as ensuring system security, has become an essential issue (Zhang, S., & Yao, Z., 2025).

Discussions

This paper explores the application of augmented reality technology in accounting education and conducts a comprehensive and cutting-edge analysis of its application scenarios and related technologies, including the types of devices used, advantages and limitations. The results show that AR technology has been gradually conducted to accounting teaching, it can improve students' learning performance and practical skills, and offer powerful assistance for the advance of accounting education. Although Augmented Reality technology has brought numerous chances, its widespread promotion still faces some challenges. This paper aims to scrutinize these issues in depth and propose feasible coping strategies to offer a reference for the further progress of augmented reality technology in accounting education.

Conclusion

This study systematically uses the methods of research questions of systematic review and meta-analysis to sort out the research on the application of augmented reality technology in accounting education from 2020 to 2025. Through the analysis of four studies, we summarize the current status, advantages, and disadvantages. Firstly, the study shows that since 2020, there have been four studies in this article. Secondly, practice has shown that it has significantly improved students' learning performance. The visual teaching method adopted by augmented reality helps students better understand complex content and enhance the lasting memory of knowledge. This teaching method shows apparent advantages in enhancing the knowledge shift procedure as well as enlightening teaching interaction. The research results state that augmented reality technology can significantly improve the teaching quality and general effect of accounting education.

Limitations and future work

As a systematic review, the article still contains some limitations. First, this paper selected only three major databases (ProQuest, Web of Science, Scopus) for the literature search. Although they cover a great deal of academic resources, relevant studies in other databases may still be missed. Second, due to the strict screening criteria, which are limited to English and AR in accounting studies, some potentially valuable research results published in non-English environments or non-related topic studies may be excluded. Thirdly, the time is limited to 2020-2025.

To address the problems mentioned above and further explore the potential applications of augmented reality technology in accounting education, additional research can be conducted in the following aspects. To overcome the above problems and further explore the application potential of augmented reality technology in accounting education, future research can be carried out from the following aspects. Firstly, researchers can design and implement more field experiments to evaluate the effect of augmented reality technology in specific teaching scenarios through empirical research, so as to obtain first-hand data. Secondly, by establishing a data-driven feedback mechanism, it is not only possible to more objectively evaluate the actual effectiveness of AR teaching tools, but also to provide a scientific basis for the dynamic optimization of teaching strategies, thereby continuously improving teaching quality and learning outcomes.

DISCLOSURE STATEMENT

No potential conflict of interest

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Author Information

Renren Cao

Centre for Instructional Technology and Multimedia,
Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia

Wan Ahmad Jaafar Wan Yahaya

Centre for Instructional Technology and Multimedia,
Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia

Tan Li

Centre for Instructional Technology and Multimedia,
Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia

Kien Tsong Chau (Corresponding Author)

Centre for Instructional Technology and Multimedia,
Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia

Chen Yan

Centre for Instructional Technology and Multimedia,
Universiti Sains Malaysia, Penang, Malaysia